

WAYS TO DEVELOP COOPERATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE REGION.

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Abstract. The article discusses the development of integrated cooperation of higher education and professional educational institutions in Uzbekistan. Cooperation between higher education and professional educational institutions is considered to be a factor leading to the improvement of the quality of education, the production of qualified specialists, and the development of the economy.

Key words: higher education, professional education, technical schools, integration, integrated cooperation, quality of education, science, qualified specialists, spiritual and intellectual field, professional qualification, innovative education.

The training of highly qualified specialists according to world standards is largely related to the sustainable development of higher and vocational education and integrated cooperation. This, in turn, requires the organization of this educational process based on the requirements of advanced pedagogical technologies and the continuous integration of higher education and professional education. At the same time, it is necessary to organize the educational process taking into account the requirements of our national economy, to introduce relevant teaching technologies, and to improve the methodological support aimed at constantly updating the educational content.

The deeper and more branched a tree's roots are, the stronger it is, the longer its life, and the more plentiful its harvest. Humanity has not been able to discover a more effective tool for the development of society than education, science and craft during its many thousand years of development. For this reason, education and science are an important factor that determines the future of any society, nation and state and serves its development.

Education can achieve its intended results only if it is able to connect its roots with science and production, social life, in a word, with life, and if it enters into comprehensive integration with internal and related networks. and a state that is able to provide a deep, all-round continuous connection of science, education and economy and is able to apply it to all spheres of society's life will achieve progress. In this regard, it is no secret that significant work is being done in the field of education of our country. Fundamental improvement of the education system, determination of the target areas of training of highly educated specialists, especially continuous improvement of the professional qualifications and knowledge level of pedagogues are among the most urgent issues. It is no coincidence that in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis on the most important priorities for 2019, special emphasis is placed on science and education, education and socio-economic life relations among the current issues. it's not. As long as the human capital is at the center of the education system, its proper distribution, its effective use and targeted orientation, in this system of pre-school, general secondary and higher education, all stakeholders of the society,

education It is one of the important tasks before us to organize the education system in a unified whole with all the subjects of the educational process based on today's requirements and to achieve complete continuity of education.

Development of the aesthetic worldview, which is considered an important component of the education of a well-rounded individual, in combination with highly qualified pedagogues-employees working in the higher education system and modern teaching technologies in the training of future specialists in professional educational institutions, and from a pedagogical point of view it is considered relevant as it aims to research and bring it to a new quality level. In our country, as a continuation of this direction, great attention is being paid to science, art, literature, and enlightenment, among other fields. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, "further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the opportunities of quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in line with the modern needs of the labor market" was set as the first priority task. This will pave the way for our country to find further progress in the future and become a "roadmap" for reform in the next five years.

Before thinking about the integration cooperation of higher education and professional education institutions, let's define the word "integration". Integration is a very broad concept. Today, it is necessary for people to understand the essence of the integration process.

What is integration? - "Integration" is derived from the Latin word "integration", and "integre" means a whole, a whole; Integration means to develop in an interconnected manner, to combine into a whole, to make a whole. Integration is the process of combining different parts and elements into a whole.

In the philosophy of Herbert Spencer (1820–1903), a dispersed, imperceptible state is understood as densification and transition to a perceptible level as a result of the slowing down of its internal processes, while disintegration is the opposite, that is, the transition of a dense object to a dispersed state as a result of acceleration of movement. Spencer uses the word "integration" often synonymously with the concept of aggregation. According to his theory, the evolution of the solar system, the planets, the organism, the nation is a succession of integration and disintegration. is the result.

In the psychology of Jaensch, Erich R (1883–1940), integration is understood as the influence of certain features of mental life on the whole set of spiritual life.

According to Rudolph Smend's doctrine of the state, integration is understood as the continuous renewal of the state as a result of the interaction of its forms of activity.

Social integration means the existence of an orderly relationship between individuals, groups, organizations and states. When analyzing the integration process, the complexity of the related system or field is taken into account. For example, integration in society, integration in civilization, integration in science, etc. The integration of society or some countries is introduced on the basis of mandatory mutual interest or goal, aspiration, value, etc. Currently, the processes of interstate integration are developing.

Integration is an objective life process. Maintaining independence in the process of integration of today's globalized life is becoming an urgent task. This requires strict adherence to the following principles in international cooperation:

It is necessary to join integrated associations only on the basis of equality of parties (even if the political and economic potential is different);

Basing on the declaration of national interests, their priority over regional and other interests;

Voluntary participation and the possibility to criticize this or that alliance.

One of the important features of modern development is the interdependence of the economies of different countries, the development of economic growth and integration processes at the macro and micro levels, the rapid transition of modern countries from a closed national economy to an open economy oriented to the outside world. is determined by the tooth. All this is explained by the laws of economic development of the world economy at the current stage.

Economic integration should not be understood simply as a natural market process or only as a consciously regulated process. It is a dialectical phenomenon that reveals both objective and subjective aspects of the same phenomenon. Integration is achieved first of all as a result of effective use of regionally important natural and raw material resources and as a result of harmonizing the interests of two or more countries.

The starting point of integration is the direct international economic relations within the primary subjects of economic life, and as their development deepens and expands, national economies gradually level their foundations. ensures that they merge with each other. And this process, the integration of the economic, legal, tax, social and other systems of the states will undoubtedly continue until the integration of the administrative structures to a certain extent.

The main goal of integration is to increase the volume of offered goods and services and expand their selection based on ensuring the efficiency of economic activity on an international scale.

"Cooperation and Integration Projects for Central Asia" published by the Institute of Central Asia and the Caucasus (Moscow) and the Alexander Knyazev Public Foundation (Bishkek) as a result of the conference held in Khojand, Republic of Tajikistan on June 26-28, 2020 : comparative analysis, opportunity and prospects" collection was published. Participants of the conference and authors of articles were prominent scientists from Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Russia, Great Britain, Italy and France.

The concept of "integration" cannot be premature. The integration process itself can take place at different levels and at different speeds. Here, it is only necessary to specify the extent to which integration is proposed to be considered. Many came to the conclusion that since the emergence of independent states in Central Asia, not enough time has passed to fully understand the direction of these processes. This is a huge task that requires a careful calculation of the amount of natural resources in each country, the possibility of redistributing them in a way that does not harm the people, and the calculation of the current level of development of the economy of each country... It is also it is necessary to take into account the ambitions of the leaders of the regional countries."

Indeed, in recent years, the Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has begun to pay serious attention to reforming the education sector, fundamentally improving the quality of personnel training, and in particular, applying the experience of developed foreign countries to the system. The reforms in this regard are based on the "Measures to further improve the activities of secondary special and vocational education institutions" dated March 14, 2017, and the "Measures to further develop the higher education system" dated April 20, 2017. "on" dated May 22, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of post-secondary

education", dated August 8, 2017 "On the activities of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on improvement" and reflected in the Presidential Decree "On the establishment of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated September 30, 2017. If we pay attention, we can see that almost all types of continuous education system are covered in these decisions. In addition, in the "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" attention is focused on fundamental improvement of the education sector. All of these documents aimed at the development and improvement of the educational system have common aspects related to the introduction of innovations in the field, assimilation of foreign experiences, support of creative approaches, strengthening of integration processes between types of education.

In our opinion, for the development of integrated cooperation of higher education and professional education institutions in Uzbekistan, the following should be given importance:

The main goal of the integrated cooperation is the educational-scientific-innovative competence that is part of it, not only with a high level of citizenship and professional competence, but also with competitiveness, the ability to accept innovations, and the ability to design and implement new educational programs and technologies. unite for the training of modern education specialists;

management and organization of education in the process of integrated cooperation, ensuring coherence and integration between types and directions of education, using teaching methods and tools;

Departments that serve as educational and experimental bases for students, masters and doctoral students studying in professional educational institutions, conducting pedagogical practice, conducting educational, scientific research, innovative and design activities. , organization of educational laboratories;

professional educational institutions:

a) scientific and scientific-methodical structures, centers, scientific research institutes engaged in collaborative scientific-research activity and defining it;

b) pedagogical communities, initiative communities, public associations, state and non-state organizations;

c) establishing integrated cooperation with foreign higher education institutions and scientific centers.

In our opinion, higher education and professional educational institutions should set the following as their main goals when establishing an integrated cooperation:

creating an environment for training future specialists based on practices with innovative experience;

shortening the period of acquisition of professional skills by young professionals;

increase the scientific, scientific-pedagogical competence of teachers of higher education and professional educational institutions;

integration of intellectual resources around current issues of development of higher education and professional educational institutions;

to find different forms and types of education, science and production practices and apply them to education;

improvement of the mechanisms that ensure the integrity of education and training;

creating an opportunity to quickly re-connect with secondary vocational education and higher education institutions and other applicants in the training of specialist personnel in professional educational institutions;

scientific justification of the need for connection, connection and cooperation between higher education and vocational colleges;

to strengthen scientific cooperation with scientific research institutes, scientific centers and base higher education institutions in order to increase the scientific potential of professors-teachers at the institute;

in order to fill the gaps in the knowledge level of teachers of professional educational institutions in cooperation with qualified professors and teachers of higher education (ETM);

establishment of scientific activities in cooperation with professors and teachers of higher education and professional educational institutions;

attracting teachers who have the ability to conduct scientific research in vocational colleges to scientific research work, etc.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that at the current stage of development of our society, the integrated cooperation of higher education and professional educational institutions provides internal and inter-industry communication in education, the experience accumulated in scientific research, scientific-methodological institutions and is being presented as the most important system in the near future that effectively implements the achievement of scientific achievements in all aspects of education and socio-economic life. In this, higher education and professional educational institutions and other interested parties of the society must be ensured of mutual and continuous communication, the final product of the educational process is the cultivation of all-round qualified specialists and scientific, creative, It is desirable to create spiritual and economic opportunities. Because we think that the level of knowledge and competitiveness of personnel is the basis of the development and competitiveness of economic production, industry, agriculture and other areas of society.

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